

LYOCELL FILAMENTS FOR CIRCULAR TEXTILES

OBJECTIVES

The CELLFIL project aims to advance and validate key production processes across the textile industry value chain, with a focus on five specific objectives to enable post-project scale-up of Lyocell filament production and achieve circular economy goals:

- Optimise Lyocell filament feedstock and yarn production
- Enhance yarn functionalisation for diverse applications
- Refine machine settings for Lyocell filament fabric development
- Develop and validate end-user textile applications for Lyocell filament
- Analyse and optimise conditions for market acceptance and large-scale production, supporting a circular textile industry in Europe

CHALLENGE

CELLFIL tackles the pressing environmental and social impacts associated with the textile industry. The global filament market is currently dominated by non-renewable materials that contribute to long degradation times and ocean pollution. There is a crucial need for sustainable, versatile, durable, and recyclable textiles. While bio-based filaments like Lyocell present a promising solution, their adoption demands significant investment and innovation across the value chain.

SOLUTION

CELLFIL is set to transform the textile industry by developing sustainable Lyocell filaments. These bio-based, biodegradable, and circular raw materials will replace synthetic fibers. CELLFIL will establish a collaborative framework to optimise the fabric production process, from raw materials to final products, and demonstrate Lyocell's versatility across over nine applications. By involving major companies, the project will drive innovation and shape market strategies, supporting a circular textile economy in Europe by 2030.

EXPECTED IMPACT

ENVIRONMENTAL

Reduced landfill waste and ocean pollution by replacing synthetic fibers with biodegradable Lyocell filaments which mitigate environmental impact of the textile industry.

ECONOMIC

Optimised technologies and business parameters for upscaled, sustainable production of Lyocell filaments for textiles and products with improved recyclability.

SOCIAL

A sustainable and competitive European textile industry achieved through the adoption of Lyocell filament production across the value chain.

CELLFIL FACTS

- EU Contribution: € 6, 999, 973
- Total cost: € 8,838, 209
- Duration: 48 months
- Start date: 1 June 2024
- End date: 31 May 2028
- Funding program: Horizon Europe
- Consortium: 15 partners from research and industry

PROJECT CONCEPT

Sustainable innovation in textiles is difficult due to industry fragmentation. CELLFIL will unify the value chain to advance Lyocell filaments from pilot to commercial scale. With development at an advanced pilot phase and led by industry experts, CELLFIL will bridge research gaps and push the limits of sustainable textiles.

The project will develop and utilise alternative raw materials, such as orange peel, wood, textile waste, and other second-generation feedstocks, for textile production. By optimising the entire fabric production process and its intermediate steps, the project aims to replace synthetic fibers with environmentally friendly lyocell filaments for use in recyclable end applications.

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